

A Survey on E-Guide to Educational Tour Planning in Environmental Science among Standard Six Primary School Students the Ministry of Education Malaysia

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Abstract—This study aims to assess the students' needs for the tour planning e-guide. The study is developing on the contribution and importance of the Educational Tour Planning Guide (ETP) is a multimedia course ware as one of the effective methods in teaching and learning of environmental science among the students in primary schools of the Ministry of Education, Malaysia. It is to provide the student with knowledge and experience about tourism, environmental science activities and process. E-guide to ETP also hopes to strengthen the student understanding toward the subject learn in the tourism environmental science. In order to assess the student's needs on the e-Guide to Educational Tour Planning in Environmental Science, the study has produced a similar e-Guide to ETP in the form as a course ware to be tested during the study. The study has involved several steps in order to be completed. It is such as the formulation of the problem, the review of the literature, the formulation of the study methodology, the production of the e-Guide to ETP, field survey and finally the analyses and discussion made on the data gathered during the study. The survey has involved 100 respondents among the students in standard six primary schools in Kluang Johor. Through the findings, the study indicates that the current tested product is acceptable among the students in learning environmental science as a guide to plan for the tour. The findings also show a slight difference between the respondents who are using the e-Guide to ETP, and those who are not on the basis of the e-Guide to ETP results. Due the important for the study, the researcher hopes to be having a fair discussion and excellence, recommendation for the development of the product of the current study. This report is written also important to provide a written reference for the future related study.

Keywords—Tour planning e-guide, educational tour planning guide, environmental science, multimedia course ware.

I. INTRODUCTION

TOURISM is a major force in global trade. It plays a vital role in the social, cultural and economic development of most nations, and has the potential both to preserve heritage and to destroy it. Despite the importance of the industry, reliable, verifiable and objective information can be frustratingly difficult to obtain [1].

Explaining travel behavior is not easy. There are just too many factors that influence an individual's behavior, and the factors noted here are recognized as major sources of influence on this type of behavior. Each of these factors is

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perception, learning, personality, motivation, attitude, and the effects group [1].

This study is aimed to explore the needs of e-tourism guide students in primary schools Kluang Johor. It is based on environmental education in tourism, education among primary school students and to study the growth of tourism industry in Malaysia. Environmental education programs are seen as one of the effective methods of learning in tourism studies. Therefore, it is essential to develop e-tourism, environmental planning guide.

Environmental education refers to learning to understand human interaction with the environment and how the environment is managed prudently and responsibly towards sustainability of life on earth. Environmental education includes education about the environment [8]. According to [2] educations for the environment are closely related to individual responsibility and empathy in attitude and positive action. The goal of environmental education in school is to produce students who are more alert and attentive to the issues of the environment and obtaining knowledge, skills, values and commitment to work and act individually or together towards a solution of environmental issues.

Environmental education in Malaysia started in 1998 with the publication of the Handbook of environmental education teachers across the curriculum by the Curriculum Development Centre of the Ministry of Education for use by teachers in primary and secondary schools [4]. Incorporation of efforts on the environment is also supported by government agencies such as the Department of environment which actively organize a wide range of environmental activities involving school [3].

According to [5] the environmental education program for students is conducted by tourist activities to increase the environmental awareness and motivation for integrating environmental education across the curriculum. In a separate study conducted among students in primary schools, found 42% of respondents indicating concern for environmental issues, while 52% have never been involved in activities related to the environment. Although already almost 25 years of Environmental Education started in Malaysia, the effectiveness of this initiative among primary school pupils is still not much known. Associated students environmental awareness is important to review because environmental education opportunities created in the content of the

curriculum does not necessarily produce the desired effects of learning.

Environmental education across the curriculum and the curriculum in primary schools is much related to technical education. On this topic, students were found to be quite weak in capturing something terminology, understand a map, measure and is unable to associate the topic with experience and their environment. Students have also been revealed about how measuring and drawing a by using a certain scale, measure the coordinates of the point, the method of collection, recording data, construction schedules and graphs, draw a sketch map, review of terrain, weather research, environmental issues, etc. Understanding terms like the point coordinates, relative, absolute, scale, a range and so on in the environmental education is very important [1].

According to [4] teacher's usually practicing chalk and talk or one way teaching and learning by providing notes and information while students receive it. This method is more focused on the teacher as the main source for help and information. Although this method saves time teachers and State-controlled, but the lack of classes manifest in this technique is that it failed to create an effective learning environment that can attract and learn students on an ongoing basis. Agreed by [6] students are finding more depending on the notes and explanations given by teachers, bored and have no public opinion on the problems arising during the process of teaching and learning, the term or solve a problem which is quite difficult [7].

The report on the educational tour: Asian Children Libraries found that after the tour program, the group has gained a new knowledge on the latest improvement in their field, which is about children's literature and librarian not only on the destination of their visits, but the objective of the educational tour program is to exchange views and to share objective of the educational tour program is to exchange views and to share information on the development of children's literature in Asia. Furthermore, the importance of the educational tour that provides the group with wide knowledge and new experience.

Students can also enhance their own knowledge of their study [7]. The purpose of this study can be stated as follows;

- i. To comprehend the effectiveness of the e-Guide for the planning of Educational Tour Program (ETP).
- ii. To gain sight of the influences of the e-Guide ETP in order to persuade the tour group to have more value for money in their Educational Tour Program.
- iii. To provide some information and references for the future study or any Education's purpose. Furthermore the resulting gain from this research will benefit the e-Guide ETP user in improving their understanding about the high quality of Educational Tour Program through a proper planning.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

E-Guides for environmental tourism programs for primary school children are a very interesting approach to learning. Learning approachable to attract and motivate students to

learn and keep learning relevant to the subject of environmental education. However, to control e-guide to the Travel Security environment is not easy, with only brings students directly to a selected destination and travelling education program continues to run [8]. Without tourism, education program planning carefully, a group of students will face many dangers and difficulties problem in implementing environmental education tourism. These activities make students do not achieve their learning objectives. An e-Guide for travel, education programs can help to reduce the student experience problems when conducting environmental education tourism program [2].

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- i. To review the needs of e-Guides for the environmental tourism programs for primary schools in Kluang, Johor Malaysia.
- ii. To enhance the understanding of the e-Travel Guide for the education among the students of primary school Kluang, Johor Malaysia.
- iii. To understand the anxiety level of students in e-Guide for the tourism program in primary schools in Kluang, Johor Malaysia.

IV. THE REVIEW OF RELATED RESEARCH

Educational tourism refers to any program in which participants travel to a location as a group with the primary purpose of engaging in a learning experience directly. Educational tourism with great potential is a new market segment in Malaysia's economic agenda. In the 9th Malaysia Plan, Malaysia revenue from this sector increased from RM 220 million in 2000 to RM 450 million in 2005. Among the educational advantages of tourist attractions in Malaysia are offering high quality education, diverse selection of courses, tuition fees are reasonable, the widespread application of educational technology, and the existence of multiple choice institutes of higher education whether public or private. In short, political stability and encouraging economic growth is fundamental in realizing Malaysia as a leading educational travel hub in the Asia Pacific region in particular and the world in general [1].

The Student Tourism Program was launched on February 24, 2001 by the Minister of Culture, Arts and Tourism Malaysia together with The Minister of Education. The main goals of this program are to promote domestic tourism activity to foster cultural tourism among students in order to travel to places of historical, cultural, eco-tourism and others; avoid social phenomena a rising among students nowadays by filling their leisure time wisely and beneficial; and create unity and to improve the integration of the younger generation through tourism activities and adventures planned and organized in order to strengthen the relationship and interaction between students of different races.

The Education Tourism Program is a form of tourism that is embedded in the integrated education system. It is more

focused on tourism activities that have elements of education through the School Travel Club. The Tourism Education Program provides early exposure of the tourism industry in terms of career opportunities, tourism and components it can generate student thinking towards the tourism industry through a number of aspects. This study aims to identify the extent of implementation of the Education Program of Tourism through Tourism Club in generating the minds of students to "Think Tourism". The sample was composed of 70 teachers in the school counselor about Touring Club in Selangor. The instrument used in this study questionnaire. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 11.5 to get the percentage and total score. The study found that the role of the Tourism Club in generating the minds of students to "Think Tourism" is at a high level. This is based on an average of 4:32 min. Availability of teachers in the Tourism Education Program is conducted at a high level with the mean score 3.90. While in terms of sustainability management in Tourism Education Program conducted in schools, the mean value obtained was 3.31. This value is moderate [6].

V. METHOD

A. Research Design

This study was conducted in the quantitative research form through a descriptive survey method which uses a questionnaire. Data gathered by using a questionnaire which circulated to respondents to seek relevant information related to this study.

B. Samples

There were 160 students of primary school in Kluang Johor Malaysia. The desired size of the sample for the study is 100. The samples are determined into subgroups based on the use of the e-Guide of Educational Tourism Program.

C. Data Analysis Method

The raw data were being gathered and quantitatively analyzed. Data analysis for this study was carried out by using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (Version 20). This data is analyzed, then used to find the mean level

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. To review the needs of e-Guides for the environmental tourism programs for primary schools in Kluang, Johor Malaysia

Five questions item regarding the level of the needs of e-Guides for the environmental tourism program being asked to the respondents. Based on assessment of respondents, the mean score for item 1 to 5 are such as show in Table I. The mean score for item 1 to 5 are such as show in Table I. Based on Table I the survey indicates that among 100 students of the primary schools in Kluang, Johor, Malaysia who used an e-Guide for the environmental tourism programs show the most highly agreed (mean=4.26) to the item- it was easy and convenient to have info e-Guide for ETP and the item will

planning an e-Guide for the environmental tourism program. The second highly agreed mean's levels (mean=4.15) are for item no.1, and the minimum highly agreed means' value (mean=3.86) is item no 4. The finding shows the overall interpretation for review the needs of e-Guides for the environmental tourism programs for primary schools in Kluang, Johor Malaysia.

TABLE I
TO REVIEW THE NEEDS OF E-GUIDES FOR THE ENVIRONMENTAL TOURISM PROGRAMS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN KLUANG, JOHOR MALAYSIA

No	Item	Mean	Mean Interpretation
1	I wanted up-to-date information about e-Guides for The Environment Tourism Program.	4.15	High
2	I saw the e-Guides for The Environmental Tourism Program.	4.15	High
3	It was easy and convenient to have the info	4.26	High
4	I like to organize e-Guides for The Environmental Tourism Program.	3.86	High
5	I will be planning an e-Guides for The Environmental Tourism Program sometime soon	4.26	High
Overall Interpretation		4.14	High

TABLE II
TO ENHANCE STUDENTS' UNDERSTANDING E-GUIDE FOR THE EDUCATION TOURISM PROGRAM

No	Item	Mean	Mean Interpretation
6	Set the objectives	2.54	Moderate
7	Designing an itinerary	2.62	Moderate
8	What to see and do	2.60	Moderate
9	Where to stay	2.34	Moderate
10	Creating a budget	2.60	Moderate
11	Special event or performances	2.30	Low
Overall Interpretation		2.50	Moderate

A. To Enhance Students' Understanding e-Guide for the Education Tourism Program

Table II indicates the finding on the level of how helpful were ETP e-Guide in the planning for the educational tourism program. The findings show that the level of somewhat helpful and very helpful indicates the highest response in all six categories. Table II also shows that the ETP e-Guide are very helpful in guiding the user on what to see and do (mean=2.60) on the level of very helpful. The mean value is 2.60, fall into the moderately high level of the e-Guide effectiveness. In creating a budget e-Guide is equally helpful as finding indicates the mean value is 2.60. However, as shown in Table II, ETP e-Guide indicates the significantly lower contribution on special event or performance planning among all other categories as shown in the mean value column, which is shown as low as 2.30 but still indicates of moderately high level of the e-Guide effectiveness.

VII. CONCLUSION

From the research, analysis, it shows that respondents agree with the usage of e-Guide for the Education Tourism Program as a tool to develop a basic itinerary in the environmental education tour program. It is an activity that involves a big

sum of money, valuable time and energy to travel and visit to other places as a destination to gain more knowledge or learning in environmental education subject

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